

The Effects of Shariah Supervisory Board and Good Corporate Governance on Islamic Social Responsibility in Shariah Commercial Banks In Indonesia

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Abstract

this study aims to analyze the effects of Shariah Supervisory Board (DPS) and Good Corporate Governance (GCG) on Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR) in Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia. Shariah banking industry is one sector that is required to include ICSR as one technique to organize their business, which is important not only to shareholders but also to other stakeholders. Furthermore, ICSR represents a challenge to preserve the reputation of shariah banking for the welfare of the community. This study uses the SmartPLS application and Structure Equation Model (SEM) technique for data analysis and. It is a descriptive and quantitative study with secondary data, in which the populations are 13 Shariah Commercial Banks (BUS) in Indonesia, Shariah Supervisory Board, the proportion of Independent Commissioners, the number of the Board of Commissioners meeting, the proportion of the Audit Committee, the number of Audit Committee meetings in Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia in 5 years period (2013-2017). Interestingly, this study found that Shariah Supervisory Board positively and Keywords Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility, that the proportion of the Board of Independent Commissioners positively and significantly affects Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility, that the size of the Board of Commissioners positively and positively and Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility. However, this study found that the size of the Audit Committee has no effect on Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility and neither does the number of Audit Committee meetings on Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility. The results of this study are expected to be useful, especially to Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia, in improving the significantly affects the welfare of the community through optimal implementation of Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility, which ultimately leads to better community trust on shariah banking

Keywords: Shariah Supervisory Board, Board of Commissioners, Audit Committee, Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility

1. Introduction

The growth of an entity is inseparable from the social lives around it. Fauziah and Yudho (2013) in Amalina (2014) underline that a large number of industries, including the banking sector, must provide social responsibilities to the environment that cover three elements, namely economy (profit), social (community), and environment (planet). Social responsibilities in an entity should have in their goals the growth of community and environment around them. This growth includes the contribution to improving the quality of life of workers and their families in the entity, including the social community (Amalina, 2014). The contribution may derive from operational gain or assets owned by the entity. The most common forms of contribution a refund donation and public social activities.

In Indonesia, social reporting is regulated in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 40 of 2007 on Limited Liability Company, article 66 and 74. In article 66, limited liability companies are required to report annual reports that at least contain a financial statement, an activity report, a social and environmental responsibility performance statement, details of problems, a supervision report, and listing of the company's directors and their salaries and allowances. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is an approach where a company integrates social conscience in their business operation and interaction with the stakeholders based on the principles of volunteerism and partnership (Nuryana, 2005). CSR is, in Islamic perspectives, an inherent consequence of the teaching of Islam itself. The purpose of Islamic law (*Maqashid al Syariah*) is *maslahah*, that is, the goal of a business is creating *maslahah*, in addition to gaining profit. In Islam, businesses hold the noble and strategic role as not only it is allowed but also encouraged by Allah in Qur'an.

Good company management or commonly known as Good Corporate Governance plays an important role in company success. Good corporate governance is expected to conduct supervision and management to generate added-value for the company. Board of commissioners that is independent in general has better supervision on the management which will affect financial statement by the manager, in other words, the more competent the board of commissioners, the lower the possibility of fraud in the financial statement (Chtourou, et al., 2001). Audit committee has quite an important role in realizing good corporate governance for it is part of the board of commissioners that supervise the company. An audit committee is tasked to provide a professional and independent opinion to the board of commissioners on reports and other matters expressed by directors to the board of commissioners, and to identify issues that necessitate concerns of the board of commissioners (Effendi, 2009). With good corporate governance, information asymmetry is expected to be mitigated.

Priantana and Yustian (2011) stated that the size of the board of commissioners positively affects the disclosure of CSR. A study conducted by Aini and Cahyonowati (2011) showed that the size of the board of commissioners positively affects the disclosure of CSR. While according to Waryanto's (2010) study, the size of the board commissioners does not significantly affect the disclosure of CSR.

Based on the study background above, this study will analyze the effects of Shariah Supervisory Board (DPS), Good Corporate Governance (GCG) with its components as dependent variables against Corporate Social Responsibilities as independent variables in Shariah Commercial Bank (BUS) in Indonesia.

The problems in this study are:

1. How does the Shariah Supervisory Board affect Islamic Corporate Social Responsibilities of Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia?
2. How does Independent Board of Commissioners affect Islamic Corporate Social Responsibilities of Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia?
3. How does the size of the independent board of commissioners affect Islamic Corporate Social Responsibilities of Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia?
4. How does the size of audit committee affect Islamic Corporate Social Responsibilities of Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia?
5. How does the number of audit committee meetings affect Islamic Corporate Social Responsibilities of Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia?

2. Literature Study

2.1. Tawhidi String Relation (TSR) Approach

According to Islamic epistemology, all knowledge is based on Qur'an and Sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad. The problems faced will be analyzed with this knowledge. According to Chouduty (2002), in Tawhidi String Relation, Qur'an is the source of knowledge, where Qur'an is a religious text/revelation that accounts the Oneness of Allah known as Tawhid. Qur'an is given to mankind so that mankind establishes life order based on the behavior of the Prophet Muhammad. According to epistemology, it is symbolized with (Ω , S), according to Qur'an, the knowledge is a revelation sent to mankind through shuratic process. Shuratic process is a process pertaining to human and nature, in this system strong interaction will occur.

2.2. Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory is a theory that considers all concerned parties in the company in wide scope (Musibah and Wan Sulaiman, 2014). This theory shows the effect exhibited by the company on entire stakeholders, ranging from shareholders, investors, creditors, workers, suppliers, to business partners and concerned external parties.

2.3. Resource Dependency Theory

It is a theory that influences the crucial role played by organization leaders in providing and maintaining resources essential to the company through their influence on the external sphere (Musibah and Wan Sulaiman, 2014). A company as an organization is heavily reliant on resource supplies for its operation. Preffer (1978) mentioned three main factors that define the dependency in the provision of the resources.

2.4. Resource Based Theory

Resource based theory is a theory pioneered by Penrose (1959). This theory points out that companies are dependent on a group of heterogeneous resources with different capabilities (Musibah and Wan Sulaiman, 2014). Resources in companies can be financial resources, tangible and intangible assets such as culture, company name, and human capital.

2.5. Shariah Supervisory Board (DPS)

Shariah supervisory board is a body that supervises the performance of DSN decision in shariah financial institutions. DPS is appointed and dismissed in a shariah financial institution through RUPS by the recommendation of DSN (Muhammad Firdaus et al., 2007).

2.6. Good Corporate Governance (GCG) Concept

The concept of Good Corporate Governance is proposed in order to achieve performance improvement through supervision or monitoring of management performance and to ensure management accountability toward stakeholders by basing it on the regulatory framework. Furthermore, the concept of corporate governance is put forward for the sake of achieving more transparent company management to all parties concerned with the financial statement (Oktafia, 2008). Corporate Governance arises from the separation of company ownership and management, or more commonly known as an agency problem. Corporate governance is a system regulating and managing the company which is expected to generate and boost the value of the company to the shareholders (Herawati, 2009).

2.7. Conceptual Framework

2.8. Hypotheses

1. **H1:** There is a positive effect between **Shariah Supervisory Board (DPS)** and **Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR)** on Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia.
2. **H2:** There is a positive effect between **the size of Independent Commissioners** and **Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR)** on Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia.
3. **H3:** There is a positive effect between **the number of Board of Commissioner meetings (DPS)** and **Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR)** on Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia.
4. **H4:** There is a positive effect between **the size of the Audit Committee** and **Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR)** on Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia.
5. **H5:** There is a positive effect between **the number of Audit Committee meetings** and **Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR)** on Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia.

3. Research Methods

3.1. Research Design

Basically, types of research can be classified according to the purpose, the method, the explanation stage, the analysis, and the data type. By methods, this is survey research in the form of explanation research and hypothesis testing. In the survey, the information is collected from respondents using a questionnaire whose data is collected from samples or populations (Sugiono, 2005). Based on the explanation stage and variable

position, this research is a quantitative study. Quantitative study is a questionnaire given to respondents containing questions which will be scored.

3.2. Populations and Samples

This study analyzes the effect of Shariah Supervisory Board (DPS) and Good Corporate Governance (GCG) on Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR) in annual reports of Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia from perspectives of Islam. Therefore, populations in this study are 13 Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia. Sample collection technique used in this study is purposive random sampling, which is, according to Hadi (Ghufron, 2002:67), a collection technique based on characteristics or properties of the population that have been known beforehand. The samples taken are all elements involved in this study, such as Shariah Supervisory Board, Independent Board of Commissioners, the number of Board of Commissioner meetings, the size of Audit Committee, and the number of Audit Committee meetings in Shariah Commercial Banks in Indonesia, amounting to 208 samples in total.

3.3. Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics used in this study applies the method of Structural Equation Model based on Partial Least Square (PLS) assisted by SmartPLS 2.0 m3.

3.4. Measurement Model Evaluation

The evaluation of the measurement model or the outer model is done to assess the validity and reliability of a model. An outer model with reflective indicators is evaluated through Convergent Validity and Discriminant Validity from indicators forming latent construct and Composite Reliability for its indicator block (Chin, 1998 in Latan and Ghozali, 2012).

3.5. Hypothesis Testing Method

Hypothesis testing is done by observing the significance value to identify the effects between variables. The limit to accept or reject hypotheses proposed is >1.67 (significance level = 5%) where if $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ [> 1.67 (one-tailed)], the H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. However, if $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$ [< 1.67 (one-tailed)], then H_o is accepted and H_a is rejected. In addition to observing the value of t table, to reject or accept a hypothesis, a positive or negative value of path coefficient needs to be considered.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Partial Least Square (PLS) Analysis

In this study, data analysis is done with Partial Least Square (PLS) approach using SmartPLS 3.0 M3 software. Partial Least Square (PLS) is a structural equation model (SEM) based on variance components. PLS approach is distribution-free (does not use specific distributed data, can be nominal, categorical, ordinal, interval or ratio).

4.2. Assessing Outer Model or Measurement Model

There are three criteria in the use of data analysis technique with SmartPLS to assess outer model, which are Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, and Composite Reliability. Below is the figure of PLS Algorithm in this study.

4.3. Convergent Validity

Outer Loading Table (Measurement Model)

Variables	Outer Loading
Shariah Supervisory Board	1
ISR	1
The Number of Audit Committee Meeting	1
LEVERAGE	1
Proportion	1
ROA	1
SIZE	1
UDK	1
The Size of Audit Committee	1

Source: Processed SmartPLS Data, 2019

As seen in the table, outer loading indicators for all variables have a value bigger than 0.5, therefore, individual reflective measurement is considered adequate.

4.4. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity Value (Cross Loading)

Variables	SHARIAH SUPERVISORY BOARD	ISR	THE NUMBER OF AUDIT COMMITTEE MEETINGS	LEVERAGE	THE PROPORTION OF INDEPENDENT BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS	ROA	SIZE	THE SIZE OF BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS	THE SIZE OF AUDIT COMMITTEE
Shariah Supervisory Board	1.000000	0.541224	-0.050472	0.440661	-0.321745	0.166462	0.168465	0.293490	-0.088388
ISR	0.541224	1.000000	-0.074072	0.259684	0.254122	-0.096133	0.295559	0.427959	-0.048932
The Number of Audit Committee Meetings	-0.050472	-0.074072	1.000000	-0.091779	-0.218323	-0.011570	0.485618	0.247712	0.550737
LEVERAGE	0.440661	0.259684	-0.091779	1.000000	-0.035332	0.017913	-0.031767	0.163886	-0.282237
The Proportion of Independent Board of Commissioners	-0.321745	0.254122	-0.218323	-0.035332	1.000000	-0.018195	-0.262271	-0.268611	-0.247048
ROA	0.166462	-0.096133	-0.011570	0.017913	-0.018195	1.000000	-0.054976	-0.109222	-0.015430
SIZE	0.168465	0.295559	0.485618	-0.031767	-0.262271	-0.054976	1.000000	0.641879	0.506747
UDK	0.293490	0.427959	0.247712	0.163886	-0.268611	-0.109222	0.641879	1.000000	0.203278
The Size of Audit Committee	-0.088388	-0.048932	0.550737	-0.282237	-0.247048	-0.015430	0.506747	0.203278	1.000000

Source: Processed SmartPLS Data, 2019

As seen in the table, some loading factor values for each indicator of respective latent variables do not have a loading factor that is not bigger than loading value when correlated with other latent variables. In other words, each latent variable has good discriminant validity where some latent variables do not have parameters that correlate strongly with other constructs.

4.5. Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

**Cronbach’s Alpha Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Average Variance Extracted (AVE)**

	AVE	Composite Reliability	Cronbach’s Alpha
SHARIAH SUPERVISORY BOARD	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
ISR	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
THE JUMBER OF AUDIT COMMITTEE MEETINGS	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
LEVERAGE	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
THE PROPORTION OF INDEPENDENT BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
ROA	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
SIZE	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
THE SIZE OF BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
THE SIZE OF AUDIT COMMITTEE	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000

Source: Processed SmartPLS Data, 2019

From the table, it can be concluded that all constructs meet the reliable criteria. It is shown by Cronbach’s Alpha composite reliability value bigger that 0.70 and AVE value bigger that 0.50 matching the recommended criteria.

4.6. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Structural Model (Inner Model) and GoF

	Community	R Square
SHARIAH SUPERVISORY BOARD	1	
ISR	1	0.681434
THE NUMBER OF AUDIT COMMITTEE MEETINGS	1	
LEVERAGE	1	
THE PROPORTION OF INDEPENDENT BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS	1	
ROA	1	
SIZE	1	
THE SIZE OF BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS	1	
THE SIZE OF AUDIT COMMITTEE	1	
AVERAGE	1	0.681434
GOF	0.825490157	

Source: Processed SmartPLS Data and processed Ms. Excel data, 2019. The table shows Goodness of Fit value of 0.825>0.36 GoFLarge. This indicates that the model in this study fits the data obtained.

4.7. Significance and Hypothesis Testing

Results for Inner Weights

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	Standard Error (STERR)	T Statistics ((OSTERR))
SHARIAH SUPERVISORY BOARD -> ISR	0.657649	0.642577	0.171356	0.171356	3.837910
THE NUMBER OF AUDIT COMMITTEE MEETINGS -> ISR	-0.099589	-0.110682	0.117834	0.117834	0.845163
LEVERAGE -> ISR	-0.044664	-0.035140	0.087677	0.087677	0.509417
THE PROPORTION OF INDEPENDENT BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS -> ISR	0.572120	0.581396	0.137390	0.137390	4.164215
ROA -> ISR	-0.154243	-0.147868	0.092510	0.092510	1.667315
SIZE -> ISR	0.162607	0.192175	0.134784	0.134784	1.206432
THE SIZE OF THE BOARD OF COMMISSIONERS -> ISR	0.289396	0.287924	0.134689	0.134689	2.148617
THE SIZE OF AUDIT COMMITTEE -> ISR	0.049170	0.047784	0.102103	0.102103	0.481573

Source: Processed SmartPLS Data, 2019

Based on the results presented in the table above, the coefficient value of shariah supervisory board path on ICSR is 0.657 with t count value of 3.837. The value is bigger than t table 2.012. This result shows significant effect of Shariah supervisory board on ICSR.

The coefficient value of the number of audit committee meeting path on ICSR is -0.099 with t count value of 0.945. The number is lower that t table of 2.012. The result shows insignificant value of the number of audit committee meetings on ICSR. The coefficient value of the proportion of independent board of commissioner path on ICSR is 0.572, with t count value of 4.164. The value is higher that t table 2.012. The result shows significant effect of the proportion of independent board of commissioners on ICSR.

The coefficient value of the size of the board of commissioner path on ISR is 0.289 with t count value of 2.418. The value is higher that t table of 2.012. The result shows significant effect of the size of the board of commissioners on ICSR. The coefficient value of the size of audit committee path on ISR is 0.049 with t count of 0.481. The value is lower that t table of 2.012. The result shows an insignificant effect of the size of the audit committee on ICSR.

5. Conclusions

1. ShariahSupervisoryBoardshows path coefficient value of 0.657 with t count value of 3.837. The value is bigger than t table 2.012. This result shows a significant effect of Shariah supervisory board on ICSR.

2. The proportion of Independent Board of Commissioner shows path coefficient value on ICSR of 0.572, with t count value of 4.164. The value is higher than t table of 2.012. The result shows a significant effect of the proportion of independent board of commissioners on ICSR.
3. The size of the Board of Commissioner shows path coefficient value on ICSR of 0.289 with t count value of 2.418. The value is higher than t table of 2.012. The result shows no significant effect of the size of the board of commissioners on ICSR.
4. The size of the Audit Committee shows path coefficient value on ICSR of 0.049 with t count of 0.481. The value is lower than t table of 2.012. The result shows no significant effect on the size of the audit committee on ICSR.
5. The number of Audit Committee meetings shows the path coefficient value on ICSR of -0.099 with t count value of 0.945. The number is lower than t table of 2.012. The result shows an insignificant effect of the number of audit committee meetings on ICSR.

6. Literature

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